

Euphorbia tetragona Honey Euphorbia

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 2 - 3 m

Distribution:

Located in dry subtropical and coastal areas of southern Africa, this species occurs in the Eastern Cape from Uitenhage northwest of Port Elizabeth, extending eastward and northward into KwaZulu-Natal.

Importance:

The Honey Euphorbia is an ornamental, soil-adaptable plant with nectar-rich flowers and soil-enhancing properties. However, the Euphorbiaceae family in southern Africa is increasingly threatened by illegal trade, underscoring the need for urgent conservation.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 92.1 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 15.44 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 3.25 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 74.4%, Duplicated: 25.4%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 12 081.75 kilobases

Contig number: 1 458

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